

Definition and Structure of the Concept of Linguistic Ability

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Abstract:

In this article, the importance of the attention paid to the study of foreign languages by the head of our country today, as well as the formation of the concept of linguistic ability in psychology and the approaches to its application have been considered. The importance of the ability in the formation of linguistic ability and the important ideas about the psychological processes in the process of learning one's mother tongue or a foreign language in linguistics and the results of scientific research conducted by scientists in the past were studied. Today, the importance of the concept of linguistic ability, which is important in the process of perfect learning of a foreign language by our youth, was considered. At the same time, the definition of the concept of "Ability", which is of great importance in the process of learning foreign languages, is also discussed about the science of "Linguistics" and "Linguistics Competence".

Key words: the concept of psychological knowledge, the structure of linguistic psychology, the concept of ability, psychological characteristics, linguistic competence, theoretical foundations of psycholinguistics, linguistics as a science, linguistic skills, quantitative-correlation descriptive research design, cognitive ability in linguistics, D. Carroll's cognitive psychometric approach in psychology, phonetic coding ability, structure of modern linguistics.

The article considered the initial steps taken in psycholinguistics and its consideration as a field of philosophical science. Many psychologists have focused on the importance of studying the factors of the formation of the ability to learn a language in young adolescents into orthographic, morphological, phonological and semantic parts. (Nature or nurture?), R. Sparks and L. Ganshaw's

linguistic coding ("Linguistic Coding Differences Hypoth - ") scientific and an attempt was made to reveal his theoretical works.

In the article, Gardner's development in the 1960s caused wide discussions in linguistics, that is, the perception of language through listening comprehension and learning through its gradual understanding, as well as the psychological processes that occur in the process of language learning in young children. was passed. In the process of acquiring foreign languages in young children or teenagers all over the world, they begin to synthesize new words in the process of listening and understanding through the brain, and gradually create a vocabulary of the new words they hear in their brain. researches have been studied. By modern psycholinguists, the study of language by speech perception is divided into levels: emotional, perceptual and semantic, the scientific research carried out by scientists in linguistics that in the process of language learning, attention should be paid to sound, words and text. tried to reveal about the research.

Today, the opportunities and attention created by the head of our state for young people are very great, and the importance of this imposes on us very important duties for each of us. The fact that the head of our state pays special attention to the issue of education and, in turn, the issue of carrying out education together with education is of great importance for every pedagogue. Today, as we live in such a constantly developing age, it is important to increase the psychological knowledge of our youth along with improving their knowledge and skills in order to take a place among developed countries and to train personnel who can set their goals correctly.

Paying attention to his physiological and psychological characteristics in human development helps to prepare him in advance for what kind of person he will be in the future and the difficulties he may face in achieving his goals. Today, more than 30 percent of the world's population is made up of young people. The majority of these percentages are teenagers, and the interest and demand of most of our youth to learn foreign languages is increasing. However, there are certainly problems that young people may encounter during the period of learning a foreign language, and the problems that should be paid attention to during the period of language learning. It is necessary to study to what extent the linguistic ability of young people is formed in the process of rapid and effective acquisition of foreign languages, and to determine the influence of important factors in the formation of psycholinguistic ability.

The innate or acquired ability of young people today is certainly important in achieving their goals and taking a step forward to their desired destination. In fact, most of us think that talent is innate. But every person has abilities, only when you determine what types of abilities belong to them and direct them in that direction, the desired goal will definitely be achieved. As we know from history, in the development of every field of science, there are many talented scientists, explorers, in today's language, we all know about the geniuses of their age. We can cite Alisher Navoi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Mirza Ulug'bek, Farabi, Aristotle, Leonardo da Vinci, Povlov and many other examples. If we look at history, the origin of psychology is connected with the development of many sciences. As we all know, psychology today is a multidisciplinary science. In history, many scientists who contributed to the development of psychology connected psychology with multidisciplinary sciences, such as biology, physics, chemistry, and exact sciences. they determined it through their own experiences after studying its nature.

Today, most of our young people have theoretical knowledge about psychology, but most of our young people learning a foreign language do not have enough knowledge about psycholinguistics. tried to collect data and conducted case studies on it. Before describing approaches to the study of linguistic abilities, we review a number of general studies recognized by many researchers.

The first forays into psycholinguistics were in philosophical and educational fields, mainly because they were located in departments other than the applied sciences (for example, aggregated

information about how the human brain works). Contemporary research uses biology, neuroscience, cognitive science, linguistics, and information science to study how the mind-brain processes language, as well as the social sciences, human development, communication theories, and certain processes of infant development. Psycholinguistics or the psychology of language studies the relationship between linguistic factors and psychological aspects. The discipline is primarily concerned with the mechanisms by which language is processed and expressed in the mind and brain; that is, the psychological and neurobiological factors that enable a person to acquire, use, understand and produce language. Psycholinguistics is concerned with the cognitive abilities and processes required to create the grammatical constructions of language as well as the listener's perception of these constructions.

For many years, many psychologists and linguists have conducted heated debates about the importance of foreign language skills in young teenagers. The importance of ability in language learning, or the concept of linguistic ability, and the establishment of language learning in accordance with its structure and structure. According to the general classification, abilities are divided into two groups. They are divided into general and special abilities. When determining the psycholinguistic abilities of our youth, we must have sufficient information about psychology and linguistics. Before studying the types of abilities, we must first understand what are abilities and linguistics.

Linguistic competence in linguistics is a system of unconscious knowledge that one knows when one knows a language. It is distinguished from linguistic indicators, which include all other factors that allow one to use one's language in practice. Language ability is understood as the ability to acquire a language. Children have the greatest capacity for language acquisition. This ability diminishes after about 10 years of age. Linguistics is based on the theoretical and descriptive study of language and is also related to the applied fields of linguistics and the fields of language studies that involve the study of specific languages. Language structure refers to the arrangement of words, phrases, and sentences to create well-formed syntax, which is essential for effective communication. It includes elements such as morphology, syntax and phonology. Linguistic competences are related to the use of language by expressing and explaining concepts, ideas, feelings, facts and opinions to carry out oral and written discussions. Linguistic skills are the ability to use language to communicate. This includes the ability to speak, write and understand the language. Spoken language, written language, and their associated components (i.e., receptive and expressive) each form a dynamic integrative whole from separate language domains (i.e., phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics) is a synergistic system (Berko Gleason, 2005).

Language structure requires changes that can be made in contact with speakers of other languages, and communication skills can arise from any contact situations in the conversation process. This idea reflected the general purpose of the current study. This study was designed to assess the linguistic structure and communication skills of senior secondary school students at St. Michael's College, Department of Basic Education. It specifically aims to answer the importance of factor levels in terms of organization, delivery, supporting materials and central message. Using a quantitative-correlational descriptive research design, a purposive sampling procedure, and standardized rubrics for communication skills and language structure, the results revealed that some students were insufficiently proficient. Mean and standard deviation, Kruskal-Wallis H test, multiple linear regression analysis, and Kendall (tau- β) Rank correlation were used to determine significant effects of language and communication variables. Validation by language experts for the AAC&U Oral Communication and Writing Value rubrics found that the majority of respondents did not meet the standard level of communication skills.

For a linguist, language is a form of human communication that includes phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and the speech context provided by a particular speech community.

It is a living form of communication that changes within speech communities and over time. Linguistics helps us understand our world. In addition to understanding the nuances of the world's languages, this knowledge can be used to improve interpersonal communication, contribute to translation activities, aid literacy efforts, and treat speech disorders. Linguists have identified five basic components (phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics) found in all languages. Linguistics is the scientific study of language, and its main focus is the systematic study of the characteristics of individual languages and the characteristics of language in general. Linguistics is the scientific study of language, and its main focus is the systematic study of the characteristics of individual languages and the characteristics of language in general. Linguists, also known as verbal learners, work best with words. Whether the information is oral or written, these students memorize information through the use of language. Linguistic personality refers to the unique traits and characteristics that an individual manifests through his or her language and communication style. This includes factors such as word choice, tone, rhythm and volume of speech, as well as non-verbal communication such as body language and facial expressions. Morphology is the study of the structure and form of words in a language or languages, including inflection, derivation, and compound formation. At a basic level, words are made up of 'morphemes'. These are the smallest units of meaning: roots and affixes (prefixes and suffixes).

Modern directions are presented as differential psychological studies devoted to the specific features of the manifestation of language abilities, as well as the study of the general psychological nature, in which the general dimensionality of language development related to age, gender characteristics, education and upbringing conditions is studied. At the same time, the linguistic method primarily refers to abilities related to individual differences in mastering a nominal foreign language. In this context, the researcher needs to clearly understand what language is being studied in relation to the specific ability of language acquisition. In this review, special attention is paid to works that study abilities related to foreign language learning, or the concepts of foreign researchers, which are represented by second language concepts. In Western cognitive psychology, the psychometric approach is traditionally related to the study of abilities. The selection of the main components of successful acquisition of a second language is related to the psychometric approach of D. Carroll and S. Sapon, in a sample of 5,000 thousand students, they conducted studies that included various ability tests. As a result, they were able to highlight the best topics in second language learning, successful and high-quality quick tasks. The tasks of D. Carroll and S. Sapon identified four special cognitive abilities that are the basis for successful language assimilation:

1. Phonetic coding ability (phonetic coding ability) — perception of language sounds and sound forms of words and expressions, storing and restoring them in instant memory.
2. Grammatical sensitivity ("grammatical sensitivity") - the ability to understand grammar in a foreign language and understand the role of grammar in translating words and sentences.
3. Associative learning ability ("rote learning ability") - the ability to quickly and accurately assimilate many connections between words and their meanings, as well as the ability to restore these connections when necessary.
4. Inductive learning ability ("inductive learning ability") - the general cognitive ability to see and study the effects of the rules governing the formation of words.

These components became the basis for the development of the modern Linguistic Aptitude Test (MLAT) - a linguistic method - a modern assessment test. This test is often used in linguistic research, despite criticism from some psychologists. For example, Z. Dornia believes that the main danger of using a psychometric approach to multi-plan construction language learning is that it is important, but it makes language learning difficult. As a result, "linguistic abilities refer to everything that tests of linguistic abilities measure." In the formation of linguistic ability, it is

important to implement the structural stages of the concept of ability step by step, and in modern linguistics, the main focus should be on preventing problems that may occur in language learning.

Gardner's theory, developed in the 1960s, helps teachers, coaches, and employers adapt their teaching methods to the needs of diverse learners. Verbal-linguistic learning style refers to a person's ability to think, solve problems, and learn using language. Because most of the school curriculum is taught orally, oral-linguistic learners do well in school. They can also excel in typical university settings. At the same time, it is important to remember that verbal-linguistic ability is not synonymous with intelligence. People with oral-linguistic abilities thrive in school activities such as reading and writing. They express themselves well and are usually good listeners, with a well-developed memory of the material they read and the ability to recall verbal information.

In Gardner's experiments, language impresses people with verbal-linguistic learning styles, and they enjoy learning new words and creative ways to use language, as in poetry. They may enjoy learning new languages, memorizing languages, playing word games, and reading. Oral-linguistic learners often do well on tests based on their ability to respond quickly and accurately to spoken or written instructions. This makes it easier for such students to excel on standardized tests, IQ tests, and quizzes. However, it is important to remember that language-based tests measure only one form of intelligence. People with an oral-linguistic learning style learn best when taught using oral or written materials. They prefer activities based on language thinking rather than abstract visual information. Math word problems are more engaging for verbal-linguistic learners than solving equations.

Psycholinguistics deals with the nature of the processes that occur in the brain to understand and produce language. For example, the cohort model seeks to describe how words are retrieved from the mental lexicon when a person hears or sees linguistic input. Using new non-invasive imaging techniques, recent studies seek to illuminate areas of the brain involved in language processing. Another unanswered question in psycholinguistics is whether the human ability to use syntax arises from innate mental structures or from social interaction, and whether some animals can be taught the syntax of human language. Two other major branches of psycholinguistics study first language acquisition, infant language acquisition, and second language acquisition. For adults, acquiring a second language is much more difficult than learning a first language for babies (babies can easily learn more than one mother tongue). Thus, there may be sensitive periods during which language can be easily learned. Much research in psycholinguistics has focused on how this ability develops and declines over time. Also, the more languages one knows, the easier it seems to be to learn.

There are many questions asked by psycholinguists to each other, for example, our mind, our mind has the means of production and understanding speech. But how did we get this ability? Of course, we are not able to understand and produce speech right from birth. Nevertheless, the scientific researchers conducted by the scientists show that the 4-year-old gifted children only focus on listening and listening comprehension, so they create and try to understand the language first in their brains. So, the most important factor in the process of learning a language is to be able to listen and understand the set of words that we have understood, form a vocabulary base through our mind, and then reflect it in our speech through the language. A human child goes through biological, physiological, and psychological processes to learn language. And 4-year-olds are still passive and some, though, have developed other syntactic structures to learn, along with a never-ending supply. vocabulary items, they have already overcome the most difficult obstacles in language learning. Whatever it is, it shows that the language learning process experienced by children all over the world is the same.

For several years, one of the main tasks of psycholinguists has been emphasizing that psychological processes in the process of children learning their native language or a foreign language through

two different methods: speech production and speech understanding, is an important psychological process.

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